

Curing exotherm and processing temperature of a family of epoxy resins in the light of fabrication of composites

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A group of cyanoethylated amine has been synthesised and utilised as hardener for the curing of epoxy resin. The effect of cyanoethylation of amine on their curing reaction with epoxy resin having equivalent of 189 has been studied with the help of differential scanning calorimeter. The processing temperature during the fabrication of composites is prescribed. The exotherm of such curing reaction (ΔH_c) and the degree of cyanoethylation (CEt) of the amine follow the relation, $\Delta H_c = (324-68.40 \text{ CEt}) \text{ kJ kg}^{-1}$.

Epoxy resins, one of the most coveted resins used in the manufacture of composite materials, undergo curing reaction exothermically¹⁻⁴. The very exothermic nature of epoxy curing system makes it difficult to handle bulk quantities of resin mix for fabrication of thick and large composite laminates because such composite systems consisting of resins are basically poor conductors of heat³, causing accumulation of large amount of liberated heat which leads to the development of hot spots, nonuniformity in distribution of internal stresses and degradation of properties¹⁻⁶. For example, composites based on ultrahigh molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) fabric^{3,7} may lose their dimensional stability under the processing condition of temperature and pressure if the evolution of such heat exotherm is excessively high. Therefore, from the practical standpoint, the quantity of epoxy resin in bulk to be handled during curing is determined by the degree of exotherm (ΔH_c). So prior knowledge of the magnitude of exotherm is essential while considering the processing of polymer composites. And this can be understood well in advance conveniently from the thermogram provided by differential scanning calorimeter (DSC).

The matrix resin may be characterised according to the curing temperature in a DSC thermogram. Such temperatures depend upon the desired speed of operation and resin content to be maintained in the composite laminate⁸⁻¹⁰. But during the fabrication of composite by compression moulding there is some confusion about the selection of processing temperature (i.e. the temperature at which pressure to be applied) because of the fact that there are three prominent temperatures¹⁰ in the DSC curing thermogram such as onset curing temperature (T_i), peak temperature (T_p) and final curing temperature (T_f)¹⁰. So at what temperature the pressure needs to be applied during

processing requires some justification. Therefore, such temperature is a process control parameter and it provides the proper temperature data for application of full pressure on the resin impregnated substrate or laminate in a compression or matched die mould¹.

In this communication, the selection of processing temperature and evaluation of curing exotherm of a family of epoxy system based on the diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A (DGEBA) resin and different cyanoethylated aliphatic amines synthesised are reported.

Results and Discussion

A family of hardeners was synthesised by cyanoethylation of triethylenetetramine (TETA). Curing of DGEBA epoxy resin was carried out at a particular heating rate in the presence of stoichiometric proportion of hardeners endowed with progressively increasing proportions of cyanoethyl group in the constituent amine hardener. The characteristic curing temperatures⁸⁻¹⁰, such as T_i , T_p as well as T_f and the exotherm developed (ΔH_c) during the curing of the selected resin compositions in the DSC experiment are summarised in Table 1. A typical DSC thermogram is shown in Fig. 1.

Table 1. DSC results of curing of different epoxy systems

System	Resin composition	ΔH_c $\times 10^3$ J kg^{-1}	T_i $^{\circ}\text{C}$	T_p $^{\circ}\text{C}$	T_f $^{\circ}\text{C}$
I	DGEBA + TETA	316	66	99.2	133
II	DGEBA + (monocyanoethylated-TETA)	268	70.5	104.5	144
III	DGEBA + (dicyanoethylated-TETA)	190	71.7	118.0	189.5
IV	DGEBA + (tricyanoethylated-TETA)	114	87.3	143.3	195

The dynamic scans of the resin systems showed that the sharpness of the exotherm is broadened with the incorporation of cyanoethyl moiety into the constituent hardener

Fig. 1. DSC thermogram for the curing reaction of DGEBA epoxy resin and the hardener (a) TETA and (b) tricyanoethylated-TETA

used for curing. The position and the pattern of the exotherm peak gives an indication on the systems reactivity⁸⁻¹⁰. Functionality (f) is the average number of reactive centres¹¹ which has great influence on the curing pattern. The DSC scan indicated that the reactivity for the curing is slowed down with decreasing functionality (f) of the constituent hardener amine. It was found that the temperatures for curing are increased while the exotherm is decreased with decreasing functionality of the constituent amine in the curing system. Moreover, interestingly, the DSC thermograms in question are appreciably symmetrical which implies that the distribution of networks in the matrices is more or less uniform in all the systems. More importantly, a linear relationship between the exotherm (ΔH_c) and the degree of cyanoethylation (CEt) of the amine is apparent in accordance with the equation (1)

$$\Delta H_c = (324 - 68.40 \text{ CEt}) \text{ kJ kg}^{-1} \quad (1)$$

as derived by regression analysis. The coefficient of correlation (r) for the relationship was found to be 0.9948. The calculated value of t for testing the significance of correlation coefficient is 9.92 which is, therefore, highly significant¹².

This order of enthalpy relates to the progressive deactivation effect of the cyano group in the amine. The presence of electron-withdrawing CN group in the amine reduces the electron donating ability towards opening the oxirane group of DGEBA epoxy resin; thus it makes the system less active towards crosslinking reaction in presence of the amine hardener.

The ΔH_c value indicates that the evolution of heat decreases with the use of hardener having increasing level of cyanoethylation. It is clear from the ΔH_c data that among all compositions, System I is more prone towards scorching¹³ than the rest of the systems. Thus, it would be more easier and convenient to use System IV rather than other systems (Table 1) when bulk quantities of resin are to be handled, say in a production unit, for the fabrication of very large laminates or big composite¹ structures. Curing of epoxy resin with the tricyanoethylated amine showed the highest temperature (in respect of T_g , T_p , or T_f of Table 1) for curing. Based on the assumption that the heat developed is proportional to the formation of network⁸⁻¹⁰, these DSC data imply that the crosslink density decreases for the cured matrix system associated with amine having lower functionality.

In the field of chemical technology, prepreg is generally defined as a resin-impregnated substrate – usually woven fabrics – prepared mainly for storage with desired shelf-life before fabrication of laminates or fibre reinforced plastics composite items under applied pressure. Processing technology through prepregging provides several advantages to the composites¹⁻³. Actually, the chemical technology of prepreg demands a long shelf-life. And that is rather possible with a resin system which cures slowly. The enthalpy data, curing temperatures and the pattern of thermogram implied that the speed of reaction of System IV is the slowest. Therefore, among all the systems (Table 1), System IV may be considered more suitable resin for prepregging purpose because this composition is the most sluggish towards curing.

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